

Developing didactic-mathematical knowledge on proportionality in prospective elementary school teachers

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to describe a questionnaire for assessing some specific aspects of the didactic-mathematic knowledge of prospective primary school teachers on proportionality. These aspects include: (a) to solve proportionality problems with different methods, (b) to analyse the mathematical objects put at stake, (c) to assign the corresponding algebrization levels and (d) to recognize the difficulties that students may encounter with the mathematical activity carried out in each resolution. We also present the *a priori* analysis of a task that informs on the type of epistemic analysis that students are expected to perform.

Résumé. L'objectif de cet article est de décrire un questionnaire permettant d'évaluer certains aspects spécifiques des connaissances didactiques-mathématiques des futurs enseignants du primaire sur la proportionnalité, tels que: (a) résoudre les problèmes de proportionnalité avec différentes méthodes, (b) analyser les objets mathématique mis en jeu, (c) d'affecter les niveaux d'algèbre correspondants et (d) de reconnaître les difficultés que l'élève peut rencontrer avec l'activité mathématique réalisée dans chaque résolution. Nous présentons également l'analyse *a priori* d'une tâche qui renseigne sur le type d'analyse épistémique que les élèves sont censés effectuer.

Mathematics Subject Classification (MSC): 97D99

1. Introduction

Currently there exists an increasing interest in the international community of researchers in mathematics education on the study of the competences and mathematical knowledge for teaching that help to develop plans for mathematics teacher's professional development. The research community accept that mathematics teachers should know and be able to perform the mathematical practices necessary to solve the problems that the curriculum proposes for the educational level in which they teach, and should know how to articulate them with the subsequent mathematics contents. Nevertheless, there is also a general agreement that such competence is not enough to achieve a suitable teaching. Teachers should have a specialized knowledge of the content itself, of the transformations that have to be applied to it in teaching and learning processes and of the psychological, sociological and pedagogical factors, among others, that condition these processes. In this sense, the need to design and implement training experiences that allow promoting the professional growth and developing the teachers' knowledge and competences, is evident (Chapman, 2014; Ponte and Chapman, 2016; Sadler, 2013).

The analysis of mathematic knowledge that is mobilized in order to solve problems is part of the professional competences of a mathematics teacher. They allow teachers to adjust the complexity of the task proposed to their students, understand the possible learning conflicts and to handle knowledge institutionalization. These knowledge and skills are an essential part of the epistemic and cognitive dimensions of the Didactic-Mathematical Knowledge and Competences Model

(DMKC) proposed by Godino, Giacomone, Batanero and Font (2017).

Recent international researches in mathematics education have identified that pre-service teachers have difficulties in understanding and teaching some of the proportional reasoning components (Ben-Chaim, Keret and Ilany, 2012; Livy and Vale, 2011; Riley, 2010), such as to interpret the responses of primary education students when they solve proportionality tasks (Balderas, Block and Guerra, 2014).

Frequently, teachers focus the attention on providing their students with an operational understanding sacrificing the development of a conceptual understanding (Riley, 2010).

In this paper, we describe a questionnaire for assessing some specific aspects of the didactic-mathematic knowledge of prospective primary school teachers on proportionality. We also present the *a priori* solution of a task that informs on the type of epistemic analysis that students are expected to perform.

2. Theoretical framework

A theoretical model of teachers' mathematical knowledge (Pino-Fan, Assis & Castro, 2015) within the framework of the Onto-Semiotic Approach (OSA) to mathematical knowledge and instruction (Godino, Batanero & Font, 2007) has already been designed and it is known as the DMKC model. The DMKC model (Godino et al., 2017) articulates the categories of knowledge and didactic competences of the mathematics teacher. It considers that the teacher should have *common mathematical knowledge* regarding a certain educational level where he/she teaches, as well as having an *expanded mathematical content knowledge* that allows him/her to articulate the content with higher education levels. Moreover, as some mathematical content is put at stake, it is clear that the teacher should have a *didactic-mathematical or specialized knowledge* of the different facets involved in the educational process (the epistemic, ecological, cognitive, affective, interactional and mediational facets).

According to the DMKC model the prospective teachers should also be *competent* to address the basic didactic problems that are present in the teaching. In particular, teacher should be competent to determine the configurations of mathematical objects and processes involved in the practices that determine the intended meanings of the contents (Burgos, Beltrán-Pellicer, Giacomone & Godino, 2018). To achieve a detailed analysis of the network of objects and processes involved in solving proportionality tasks, we rely on the distinction of different *algebrization levels* of mathematical practice (Godino, Aké, Gonzato & Wilhelmi, 2014):

- *Level 0 (arithmetic meaning)*: Operations with particular objects using natural, numerical, iconic, gestural languages are carried out.
- *Level 1 (proto-algebraic meaning, incipient algebrization level)*: Generic entities, properties of the algebraic structure of natural numbers and the equality as equivalence are used.
- *Level 2 (proto-algebraic meaning, intermediate algebrization level)*: Symbolic representations to refer the intensive objects involved (linked to the spatial, temporal and contextual information), and solving equations of the form $Ax = \pm B$ are used ($A, B, C \in R$).
- *Level 3 (algebraic meaning)*: Symbols are used analytically, without referring to contextual information; operations with indeterminate quantities or variables are carried out; equations of the form $Ax \pm B = Cx \pm D$ are solved ($A, B, C, D \in R$).

Concerning with the solutions of proportionality tasks, proto-algebraic meaning is centred in the notions of rate and proportion:

- The explicit recognition of the unit value in the reduction to unity procedure and the use of diagrammatic solutions can be qualified as proto-algebraic of level 1.

- Solution of a missing value problem, involves an unknown and the statement of an equation $Ax = B$; the algebraic activity performed in this case is of level 2.

Solutions based on the notion and properties of the linear function are considered of a consolidated algebrization level 3.

From the perspective of the OSA and the DMKC model, the activity of epistemic and cognitive analysis, as well as the recognition of algebrization levels in mathematical problem-solving tasks, are considered as ways to develop that knowledge (Burgos et al., 2018, Godino et al., 2014, Rivas, Godino & Castro, 2012).

3. The questionnaire

First, it is important to identify whether prospective teachers correctly distinguish and solve inverse proportionality tasks. This is an aspect of expanded content knowledge, since it is not included in primary education. Secondly, it is intended to evaluate some aspects of didactic-mathematical knowledge in the epistemic and cognitive facets, such that:

- The flexibility to solve a problem using different strategies (epistemic facet)
- To identify algebraic reasoning levels (epistemic facet)
- To recognize the difficulties that students may encounter (cognitive facet)

The problem-situation proposed to the prospective teachers is based in the solution of the following inverse proportionality task:

It is the graduation party at Gulls Institute. Seven students have been chosen to decorate the auditorium. They would need to work 21 hours to leave the room ready for the celebration. Unfortunately, before they could begin homework, four kids have become sick with chickenpox and have to stay home. How many hours will it take the remaining students to decorate the room? Describe and explain the strategy you have used to give your answer.

For this situation, the prospective teachers were asked in the questionnaire to respond the following items:

1. Solve the next problem by at least two different methods. Use the strategies you know, considering the strategies you think your pupils would use to solve it.
2. For each solution, list the practice sequence and complete the following table, by adding the necessary rows.

Sequence of elementary practices needed to solve the task	Referred objects (concepts, propositions, procedures, arguments, ...)

3. Describe what difficulties you can observe in the solution of the problem by using each strategy (for this, observe the practices, objects, and processes identified that can be potentially conflictive for the pupils).
4. Assign algebraic reasoning levels to the different solutions given in the previous point to the task, taking into account the algebraic objects and processes previously identified.

4. Expected solutions

In this section, we include the onto-semiotic configurations corresponding to two expected solutions to this task. We identify their algebrization levels and the possible difficulties that primary school pupils might encounter in their resolution. This is the kind of analysis that future teachers are

expected to be able to perform.

4.1 Epistemic configuration of an expected arithmetic solution

Sequence of elementary practices needed to solve the task	Referred objects (concepts, propositions, procedures, arguments, ...)
1. The amount of hours needed to decorate the auditorium is obtained by multiplying the number of hours that have been necessary, by the number of students that have been working together this time: $21 \times 7 = 147$.	<p>Concepts: amount of hours, amount of students, multiplication, proportionality</p> <p>Proposition: Decorating the auditorium requires 147 hours of work.</p> <p>Procedure: Multiplication</p> <p>Arguments: It is assumed that all the students have been working in the same way for all the 21 hours.</p>
2. If 4 students became sick, then $7 - 4 = 3$ students must to do all the work by themselves.	<p>Proposition: There are 3 students available to decorate the auditorium.</p> <p>Argument: based on arithmetic properties.</p>
3. Since decorating the auditorium requires 147 hours, the 3 remaining students need to work simultaneously during $147 \div 3 = 49$ hours.	<p>Proposition: 3 students need to work for 49 hours to decorate the auditorium.</p> <p>Arguments: It is assumed that all the students will work in the same way to decorate the auditorium.</p>

Having into account the practices and objects involved in this solution:

- Pupils could find difficulties with the arithmetic calculus, determining the amount of total hours needed to decorate the auditorium and to identify the proportional relation between the number of students and the number of hours that each one need to work.
- There are no concepts or properties of structural nature intervening in the practices (just arithmetic operations with natural numbers). The *algebrization level* is 0.

4.2 Epistemic configuration of an expected (proto-algebraic) solution

Sequence of elementary practices needed to solve the task	Referred objects (concepts, propositions, procedures, arguments, ...)
1. The relation between the amount of hours and the amount of students needed to decorate the auditorium is of inverse proportionality.	<p>Concepts: amount of hours, amount of students, inverse proportionality</p> <p>Proposition: Statement of practice 1</p> <p>Arguments: It is assumed that all the students will work in the same way to decorate the auditorium.</p>
2. If 4 students became sick, then $7 - 4 = 3$ students must to do all the work by themselves.	<p>Proposition: There are 3 students available to decorate the auditorium.</p> <p>Argument: based on arithmetic properties.</p>
3. Let denote by x the quantity of hours that will be taken for the remaining students to decorate the auditorium. Then $7 \times 21 = 3 \times x$.	<p>Concept: unknown</p> <p>Proposition: The product of the corresponding values of the amount of hours and the amount of students is constant.</p> <p>Argument: Relying in the properties of the inverse proportional relation</p>

4. $x = \frac{7 \times 21}{3} = \frac{147}{3} = 49$	Procedure: solve for the unknown Argument: based on practice 3 and arithmetic properties
5. Hence, the 3 remaining students need to work during 49 hours.	Proposition: Statement of practice 5 Argument: sequence of practices from 1 to 4

Having into account the practices and objects involved in this solution:

- Pupils could find difficulties recognizing the inverse proportional relation between the quantities of hours needed to decorate the room and students that will be work simultaneously to do it.
- The solution of this missing value problem, involves an unknown and the statement of an equation $Ax = B$. Hence, the algebrization level is 2.

5. Conclusions

Sowder, Armstrong, Lamon, Simon, Sowder & Thomson (1998) propose a set of recommendations for teachers' education in the field of proportional reasoning. In particular, they consider that teachers should have a deep understanding of the conceptual components of proportional reasoning and its centrality in all mathematical thinking (p. 144). In this sense, we think that the type of analysis we presented in this paper should be an instrumental competence of the mathematics teacher. This activity of epistemic reflection aimed at achieving a deep understanding, not only of the conceptual components of proportional reasoning, but also the propositional and argumentative components (Burgos et al., 2018). It also enables prospective mathematics teacher to recognize the complexity of objects and meanings inherent to the mathematical activities, identify potential conflicts, and adapt the teaching to the students' capabilities and learning objectives in order to promote activities aimed at the development of proportional reasoning from primary school onwards. Moreover, as showed by Ostermann, Leuders & Nucle (2017), formative interventions aimed at the analysis of task difficulties improved the prospective teachers' ability of understanding the performance of their students, becoming aware of the different resolution strategies.

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